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COASTAL EROSION AND ITS MANAGEMENT IN SAGAR ISLAND, SOUTH 24 PARGANAS, WEST BENGAL

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ABSTRACT

Sagar island (Hugli estuary : 21°37'-57'N, 88°02'-11'E) was started to be reclaimed from the Sundarban mangrove wetlands in 1811. Mainly due to different Government policies the island gradually became almost completely settled with a population of 149,222 (1991), naturally growing at 3.99% per year. Coastal erosion, that reduced the total supratidal area of Sagar by about a quarter within 144yr (from 284.55 km² in 1851-55 to 219.26 km² in 1997), forms the most important natural environmental hazard (NEH) affecting the island. Among other things, the erosion can primarily be related to the disturbance of morphological steady state of the Hugli estuary due to reclamation of its intertidal areas. Most of the erosion takes place episodically during tropical cyclones – the severe types of which (Beaufort force 10 or above) have a recurrence interval of 3.28 years within 100 km of the island.

The erosion management schemes of Sagar, managed by seven different agencies, include 74.5 km of marginal embankments (19.4% brick-paved), 579 ha of mangrove plantations in 11 localities and three relocation settlements. Their efficiency range from excellent to very poor. To ameliorate the existing schemes, the available resources need to be used more rationally and optimally with proper appreciation of the natural feedback mechanisms. Brick-paving of the river-facing earthen embankments and different designs for the sea-facing dykes should be considered. Formation of an apex management coordinating agency/body is also necessary. In the long run, socio-economic development, that reduces vulnerability to the NEHs, may become the best option for alleviating the erosion hazard

INTRODUCTION

A natural environmental hazard (NEH) may be defined as a naturally occurring event which is harmful to humans and cannot be considered by them as a part of normal condition or state of the environment. The harming potentiality of an NEH varies with its magnitude as well as the socio-economic conditions and political situation of the place of its impact (O'keefe *et al.* 1976). Coastal erosion, one of the most commonly addressed problems in shoreline management besides flooding, belongs more to the pervasive (low-magnitude high-frequency) end of the NEH continuum (Gares *et al.* 1994).

Sagar island (21°37'-57'N, 88°02'-11'E; Fig. 1), at the mouth of the Hugli estuary in eastern India, once formed the westernmost part of the Sundarban mangrove forests. The reclamation of this fragile ecosystem was initiated in 1811. Since it served as a source of revenue to the British Colonial Government, the island became almost wholly settled within the next 125 years (Ascoli 1921; Pargiter 1934; Lahiri 1936). According to the 1991 census, population of the island is 149,222 with a decadal growth rate of 39.9 per cent. Coastal erosion is the most important NEH that affects this population. The aims of this article are to determine the erosional rates and patterns, to evaluate the adequacy of the

existing coastal defences and to provide an integrated management plan for alleviation of the erosion hazard.

MATERIALS, METHODS AND PREVIOUS WORK

Materials and methods

Comparison of multidated materials to evaluate coastline changes is a useful worldwide practice (Carr 1980; Hooke and Kain 1982; Bird 1985; Dugdale 1990). To estimate the long term changes in the area of Sagar island, maps, charts and images of nine different years were studied for the period from 1851-55 to 1997. An *Optomech-011* optical pantagraph (magnification range : 0.25x to 4.5x) and a *Korestat A-31* photocopier (magnification range : 0.4x to 2x) were used to bring all the materials to a similar scale. Measurement of supratidal island areas was done with a Sokkia Placom KP-90N digital planimeter directly from original materials. In addition, repeated geomorphic mapping on 1:5,000 in southeastern Sagar, the most severely eroding locality of the island, was carried out during 1991-1995 to monitor short-term changes. Lastly, to evaluate the adequacy of the existing management structures resisting erosion, repeated field checks were undertaken.

PREVIOUS WORK

Recently Kumar *et al.* (1994) and Prithviraj *et al.* (1995), based on maps and images, studied the evolution of the Hugli estuary for the periods 1971-1991 and 1971-1992 respectively. The Geological Survey of India (GSI) carried out short-term seasonal geomorphic mapping of the Sagar's southern coast between 1985 and 1992 (Chakrabarti

1991; Bandyopadhyay 1994). Seasonal mapping of two isolated stretches in the same area was also undertaken by Bandyopadhyay *et al.* (1993) between 1991 and 1993 – the results of which are incorporated in the present study.

The NEH-related problems and broad-based management possibilities of the reclaimed Sundarban and the Hugli estuary region were previously discussed by Bose *et al.* (1989), Paul (1991), Chakrabarti (1995a) and Bandyopadhyay (1997a).

EROSION OF THE ISLAND

Erosion rates and patterns

During the last 144yr, accretion in isolated areas of Sagar was overwhelmingly offset by erosion, distributed unevenly over space and irrespective of the forested or deforested (reclaimed) stretches of the coast (Fig. 2 & 5; Table 1). Except between 1903 and 1904, when the northern part of Sagar got episodically detached to form the Ghoramara islet, the total supratidal area of the island reduced more or less steadily by 22.3 per cent from 284.6 km² in 1851-55 to 219.3 km² in 1997. During this period the maximum average recession rate in the sea-facing southern section of the island was 28.6 m yr⁻¹, an extremely high value in any count (Goudie 1995:194-204).

Among the 26 coastal mouzas of Sagar, 24 were affected by coastal erosion and 10 lost more than 25 per cent of their extension between 1922-23 and 1997. The ones most severely affected include Bishalakshipur mouza (area eroded : 96.8%) in the southeast, Sagar mouza (68.2%) in the southwest and the mouzas of Muriganga (61.1%), Ram-

TABLE 1 : CHANGES IN AREA AND FOREST COVER OF SAGAR ISLAND, 1851-55 TO 1997

Source ¹	Year(s) of survey/ Date of pass	Scale	Total supratidal area in km ²	Area under natural vegetation in km ²	Rate of nett erosion (-) or deposition(+) from the preceding mapping / imaging year in km ² yr ⁻¹
A. Sol : Sheet no. 121 of <i>Atlas of India</i>	1851-55	1 : 253,440 (1" ≡ 4mi)	284.55 (100%)	shown to be completely forested	—
B Sol : Sheet no. 482-S.oo	1882-83	1 : 253,440 (1" ≡ 4mi)	269.67 (94.77%)	234.78 (87.06%)	-0.50
C RSD : <i>River Hooghly : Calcutta to Saugor</i>	1904-05	1 : 80,724 (1" ≡ 1.11 naut.mi)	245.48 (86.27%)	not shown	-1.01
D Sol : Sheet no. 79C/1 and 79C/2 : First edition	1922-23	a : 63,360 (1" ≡ 1mi)	240.12 (84.39%)	89.29 (37.19%)	-0.30
E CPC : Unnamed chart	1938	1 : 145,728 (1" ≡ 2 naut.mi)	221.06 (77.69%)	not shown	-1.09
Sol : Sheet no. 79C/1 and 79C/2 : Second edition ²	1942	1 : 63,360 (1" ≡ 1mi)			
F Sol : Sheet no. 79C/1 and 79C/2 : First metric edition	1967-69	1 : 50,000 (1cm ≡ 0.5 km)	223.56 (78.57%)	5.16 (2.31%)	+0.09
G Sol : Aerial photos (mosaic of 47 photos spread in 5 runs)	6 Mar 1977	1 : 50,000 (1cm ≡ 0.5 km)	221.41 (77.81%)	4.90 (2.21%)	-0.23
H NRSA : IRS-ICLISS-3 geocoded stander FCC no. 79C01 and 79C02	6 Jan 1997	1 : 50,000 (1cm ≡ 0.5 km)	219.26 (77.05%)	3.32 (1.51%)	-0.11
					-0.45 (1851-55—1997)

1. Sol : Survey of India, RSD : River Survey Department, CPC : Calcutta Port Commissioners, NRSA : National Remote Sensing Agency, IRS : Indian Remote Sensing Satellite.

2. Only the southern part of Sagar was revised in 79C/1 of this edition, See Fig. 2E.

krishnapur (57.2%) and Shikarpur (54.8%) in the northeast of the island. The maximum erosion took place in the Shibpur-Botkhal area in the southeastern corner of Sagar where the recession

rates were as high as 23.8 m yr⁻¹ during 1922-23 – 1997 and 37.5 yr⁻¹ during 1992–1995. Here a 6 m high frontal dune belt was almost completely obliterated and two successive rows of embank-

Fig.1 Geomorphic setting of Sagar island. Mudflats and sandy mudflats are generally associated with mangrove grasses and/or herbs. (Based on 1:100,000 IRS-IB LISS-2 image, 1992. Palaeochannels in incorporated from 1:50,000 Sol aerial photos, 1977)

Fig.2 Evolution of Sagar island, 1851-55 to 1997. Abbreviations : BF = Bedford, CL = Cromallien, GM = Ghoramara, GT = Gabtala, JM = Jambu, KG = Kabasgadi, KM = Kankramari, KP = Korapara, LC = Lohachara, Lh = Lighthouse, LS = Lash's, NC = Nayachara, SB = Suparbhangra, SP = Shikarpur, (Source : A-H : refer to Table 1, inset of C : RSD, River Hugli from Kulpi to Lower Gasper Light Vessel, 1:72,625)

ments were destroyed between 1992 and 1995 (Fig. 4). Abandoned old marginal embankments, indicating past erosion, are practically ubiquitous all along the island coasts. Breaches in the existing marginal embankments, causing tidal ingression, are also commonplace in the present erosion-affected areas. (Fig. 1).

The well known Kapil temple, the most important cultural landmark of Sagar situated at Gangasagar, had to be relocated at least four times during the last one and half centuries due to coastal erosion. The earliest recorded temple (Anon. 1841, Wilson 1846) was lost to the sea by the mid-19th century, Subsequently

a number of temporary temples were in existence (O' Malley 1914:254; Mitra 1954:cvi; Ray 1971). A permanent building was constructed in 1961 but that too was destroyed by erosion. The present structure was built in 1973 some 1.5 km inside the spring tide line (Fig. 3).

In the southern sector, between Gangasagar and Basantapur, an erosion-accretion cycle got superposed on the overall eroding trend since 1922-23 (Fig. 3). The stretch retrograded during 1922-23 – 1942, prograded during 1942 – 1968-69, retrograded again during 1968-69 – 1975 and was almost stable during 1975-1997.

Another interesting feature of the changing configuration of Sagar is non-erosion of an inlet area at Collectorgunj (Shikarpur) in the northeast (Fig. 2), although portions immediately north and south of it were subjected to relentless erosion between 1922-23 and 1997 (Fig. 2D-H). At present, the region around the tidal inlet looks more like a promontory! This phenomenon might be linked to the complex shoaling patterns and hydrodynamics of the stretch around the inlet.

Erosional seasons and agents

The erosion calendar: The yearly cycles in wind, precipitation and tidal characteristics seen in the island has an important bearing on coastal erosion of Sagar (Bandyopadhyay *et al.* 1993). It is generally seen that most of the erosion takes place during the monsoons (June-September) when a destructive wave climate, increased occurrence of tropical cyclones (Table 2) and a raised local sea level (owing to increased fresh-water input or freshets) – all coincide. Beyond this season, erosion is also brought about by tropical cyclones that occur in October and November and extremely rarely in December.

During the year, the late post-monsoon period (December-January) is relatively calm and hence the magnitude of coastal erosion becomes low. Consequently, this period is the best time for repair or construction of the NEH prevention structures.

Tropical cyclones : A few hours' pounding by the extra-powerful waves and storm surge during a fully blown tropical cyclone may equal many years' worth of normal wave erosion. But,

Fig.3 Evolution of the southern coast of Sagar island, 1922-23 to 1997. (Source : A,B,C & E:refer to Table 1 by years; D : mosaic of six Sol aerialphotos spread in a single run, 25 Dec. 1975, 1:25,000)

Fig.4 Beach maps showing gradual erosion of dunes and embankments in the southernmost Sagar island. High tide line follows embankments where not shown separately. (Source : A & B : Bandyopadhyay et al 1993; C : field survey)

because the destructive potentiality of a cyclone depends on an adverse combination of a number of factors like storm-track, storm-magnitude, local sea level and tidal conditions at the place and time of its landfall (Flather and Khandker 1993; Coch 1994), it is not always possible to draw any straightforward

relationship between occurrence and magnitude of cyclones (Table 2) and amount of erosion. For example, monitoring of the erosive Shibpur -Botkhali area of Sagar between 1991 and 1995 (Fig. 4) indicated that erosion here was mostly related to failure of embankments during tropical cyclones.

TABLE 2 : TROPICAL STORMS PASSING THROUGH 100 km OF SAGAR ISLAND, 1891 TO 1995 : CLASSIFICATION & MONTHWISE DISTRIBUTION.

<i>Storm types (with maximum wind speed and Beaufort force number)</i>				
Months ¹	Distance of storm track in km	Tropical depression (<63 km h ⁻¹ , ≤ 7)	Cyclonic storm (63-87 km h ⁻¹ , ≤ 8-9)	Severe cyclonic storm (>87 km h ⁻¹ , ≤ 10-12)
May	0-50	3	1	3
	50-100	0	1	3
June	0-50	17	4	2
	50-100	6	3	1
July	0-50	21	7	5
	50-100	22	1	0
August	0-50	29	2	1
	50-100	29	4	1
September	0-50	19	3	4
	50-100	20	3	4
October	0-50	3	3	4
	50-100	5	1	0
November	0-50	0	1	2
	50-100	3	2	1
December	0-50	0	0	1
	50-100	0	0	0
May to December	0-50	92	21	22
	50-100	85	15	10
	0-100	177	36	32
Average recurrence interval (in years) ²	0-50	1.14	5.00	4.77
	50-100	1.24	7.00	10.50
	0-100	0.59	2.92	3.28

1. There is no recorded occurrence of cyclones in the Ganga-Brahmaputra delta during January-April.

2. 0.083 years = 1 month

Source : IMD (1979) for data upto 1970, India Meteorological Department for data after 1970.

The maximum erosion in this region, was caused by a relatively low magnitude system (max. wind speed at Sagar according to India Meteorological Office record: 66 km hr⁻¹), the landfall of which coincided with the spring high tides on May 16, 1995, between 10:30 and 11:40 hours Indian Standard Time and brought about widespread destruction in the entire reclaimed Sundarban region (Indian part).

The three most destructive tropical storms struck the island on 21 May, 1833, 5 October, 1864 and 17 October, 1942. The surge level of the 1833 storm was estimated at 2.1 m by Chapman (1869) and 3.1 m by O'Malley (1914:135). While for the 1864 event, it was variously estimated at 3.4 m by Hunter (1875:

259-260), 'less than 4 m' by Rundell (1903) and '4.6 m above ground level' by Beadle (1903) & O'Malley (1914:135). Adverse socio-political conditions often suppress NEH-reporting (Smith 1996: 53). Because of a similar contemporary situation almost no quantitative information is available on the impact of the 1942 event (Mittra 1991:111-112).

Probable causes of erosion

In a morphological equilibrium condition, length of a resonant macrotidal estuary (l), like the Hugli, tends to equal a quarter of the tidal wavelength (L) (Wright *et al.* 1973; Pethick 1992), that is :

$$l \rightarrow 0.25L$$

TABLE 3 : THE EXISTING COASTAL EROSION-MANAGEMENT SCHEMES OF SAGAR ISLAND : DESCRIPTION AND EVALUATION

Erosion-management projects→	1. Earthen embankments	2. Brick-paved earthen embankments
<i>Agencies responsible for implementation / repair</i>	Irrigation and Waterways Dept. of West Bengal Government, District council, Village Panchayat	Irrigation and Waterways Dept. of West Bengal Government,
<i>Dimensions/Physical parameters</i>	<i>Length</i> : 61km (mostly double and compartmented); <i>height</i> : 2.4m; <i>sea/river-ward slope</i> : 1:2; <i>Cost per metre of length</i> : Rs. 252 (1995-96 prices)	<i>Length</i> :14.5 km (everywhere double and compartmented by unpaved embankments); <i>height</i> : 3m; <i>sea/river-ward slope</i> : 1:4; <i>Cost per metre of length</i> : Rs. 2200 (1995-96 prices)
<i>Adequacy rating (5-point scale : A-E)'</i>	A-B in mangrove-fringed coast C-E in open coast	A-C in river-facing areas, either mangrove fringed or open C-D in open sea coast
<i>Main advantages</i>	(i) Low-cost structures-require little resource allocation to construct or repair. (ii) Require little skill for maintenance-can be carried out at Village Panchayet level. (iii) Work adequately as second line of coastal defence behind mangrove buffers.	(i) Quite adequate in all river-facing marginal areas of the island. (ii) Require less frequent maintenance-economic in the long run.
<i>Main disadvantages shortcomings & management problems</i>	(i) Structures are inadequate to withstand sustained storm waves. (ii) Require extensive maintenance-liable to be destroyed if the washed off materials are not replenished in time (iii) Repaired hastily and untimely just before the erosive monsoon season. (iv) Lack of coordination among managing agencies in setting repair priorities present. Political considerations in decision making is also not unheard of.	(i) Costly for an underdeveloped agrarian region. (ii) Quality of workmanship often suffers due to overt profit-motive of the sub-contractors, repair; not possible at Village Panchayet level. (iii) Procedural formalities and red tape may consume considerable time before the actual repair of a damaged section may begin. (iv) The currently used design is inadequate for sea-facing open coastal areas.

1. A = Very good E = Very poor

Again, the tidal wave length (L), is governed by the equation :

$$L = T\sqrt{gD}$$

Where T=tidal period (a constant in a given locality), g = gravitational acceleration (a constant) and D = mean depth of the estuary (the only variable). Reclamation, by restricting the area of tidal spill through marginal embankments, increases the mean depth (D) and throws an estuary out of equilibrium – to which it tries to return by active in-channel

sedimentation and bank erosion to decrease the mean depth (Pethick 1996). With its length (l) equaling 0.17 (i.e. less than a quarter) of its tidal wave length (Bandyopadhyay 1997b), this is exactly the condition the Hugli estuary is now in. This necessitates regular repairs of the damaged marginal embankments along its banks and island margins as well as huge dredging operations to prevent the navigational channels from getting silted (Sanyal and Chakrabarti 1995).

TABLE 3 : *continued*

Erosion-management projects→	1. Mangrove afforestation schemes	2. Resettlement projects
<i>Agencies responsible for implementation / repair</i>	Forest Dept. of West Bengal Government, Sundarban Development Board.	District Council, Village panchayet
<i>Dimensions/Physical parameters</i>	Since initiated in 1985, 579 ha (400 ha by Forest Dept. and the rest by Sundarban Dev. Board) have been covered by the scheme in 11 localities. <i>Avicennia sp. and Excoecaria agallocha</i> were most commonly used. <i>Regeneration</i> : 25-30% of the area covered.	Three projects were undertaken in freshly reclaimed intertidal areas-involving about 150 families (including 100 from Ghoramara village). funding of two of the schemes came from Indira Abas yojana.
<i>Adequacy rating (5-point scale : A-E)¹</i>	A-C in creek-months. D-E in other areas	A-B
<i>Main advantages</i>	(i) Once established, the mangrove patches provide efficient protection to the embankments from erosion. (ii) Work as efficient silt traps in creek months.	Provide shelter (and in one scheme, livelihood) for a group of homeless people without removing them far away from their roots.
<i>Main disadvantages shortcomings & management problems</i>	(i) Limited protected intertidal areas are available for mangrove plantation where they are mostly need- i.e. along the presently eroding sections of the coastline (Fig.1) (ii) The much-publicised scheme of coastal mangrove reforestation with shelter-bed and toe-line plantations (see MED-SDB 1992, DoF-Go WB 1994, for details) have nowhere been followed by the agencies concerned. (iv) Excessive anthropogenic manipulation (in form of trampling, collecting and grazing) affects mangrove regeneration markedly.	(i) Fresh reclamation of intertidal areas along the already-deteriorated intra-island creeks would certainly lead to their further deterioration. (ii) Fresh reclamation of intertidal areas along the coasts of the island runs risk of future erosion. (iii) Socio-political factors play a role in getting resettlement benefits.

1. A = Very good E = Very poor

For the last 200 years, the abandoned (due to an eastward tilt) southwestern section of the Ganga-Brahmaputra delta (Morgan and McIntire 1959), is also being regionally eroded because of an offshore sediment sink at the Swatch of No Ground submarine canyon (Kuehl *et al.* 1989) and autocompaction-related subsidence among other reasons (Bandyopadhyay and Bandyopadhyay 1996). Therefore, taking into consideration all the natural

and anthropogenic causes of erosion, it may be suggested that the erosional trend of Sagar is likely to continue in the future.

EROSION MANAGEMENT

Existing preventive measures and their evaluation

The most important aim of shore-line management is to provide protection from the NEHs (Townend 1993). The

Fig.5 Sequences of coastal erosion and obliteration of embankments in the area mapped in Fig. 4 (Shibpur-Botkhali). *Left Column* : The triangle in the bottom panel locates the remnant of brick-paving. *Right Column* : The last remnant of the eroded banyan tree (*Ficus benghalensis*) is indicated by a circle in the bottom panel.

TABLE 4 : COASTAL MANGROVE PLANTATION IN SAGAR ISLAND :
AREA COVERED AND PERFORMANCE 1985-1995

Year	Agency	Place	Area (ha) ¹	Growth ²	Remarks
1985	SDB	Chemaguri	5	C	First experimental plantation in Sagar
1986	SDB	Chemaguri	13	A	—
1986	SDB	Radhakrishnapur	12	C-D	—
1988	DoF	Sagar-Beguyakhali	30	C	Survived only along creek banks
1989	DoF	Shikarpur	20	B	—
1990	SDB	Dhablat	25	C	—
1990	SDB	Sumatinagar	15	B	—
1990	SDB	Radhakrishnapur	6	E	Planted area later eroded
1991	SDB	Bankimnagar	15	B	—
1991	SDB	Shibpur-Botkhali	20	C-E	Satisfactory at the Satbanki confluence, but plantation along the erosive coastal stretch failed completely.
1991	SDB	Radhakrishnapur	10	B	—
1991	DoF	Chandipur	165		[<i>Avicennia</i> and <i>Sonneratia</i> seeds were dropped from an aircraft in contiguous partly sand-covered tidal flat, the experimentation failed.
1991	DoF	Mahishmari	55	D	
1991	DoF	Beguyakhali	80		
1992	SDB	Dhablat-Chemaguri	20	B	Well established
1992	SDB	Bankimnagar	3	B	Well established
1992	SDB	Kailapar	10	B	Well established
1993	SDB	Radhakrishnapur	40	D	Planted area partly eroded
1995	DoF	Kachaberiya	15	C	—
1995	DoF	Naraharipur	20	C	Well established
1985-1995		Sagar island	579	C-D	Actual generation : 25-30% of area

Notes : 1. Source : Social Forestry Division, Sundarban Development Board (SDB), Department of Forest (DoF), Namkhana range.
2. Growth in 5-point scale A (very good) – E (very poor); based on last observation of all the sites in 1995.

existing erosion preventing and disaster management schemes (Fig. 6) of the island are described and evaluated in Table 4. Efficiency of these projects have been reduced by excessive anthropogenic manipulation, hasty and untimely repair (e.g. during early monsoons), lack of coordination among the erosion managing agencies and socio-political rather than physical considerations in setting repair priority.

Case studies

At the level of an individual site, management strategies often tend to become conservative and overlook regional trends (Ranwell 1979). Lack of clear understanding of material-

process-form relationships of the coasts and absence of a central NEH-managing body have resulted in adoption of poor management strategies in Sagar island. For example, a costly 3.2-km brick-paved coastal embankment was constructed between Raspur and Basantapur of southern Sagar (Fig. 3) in 1976-78. But during that time the entire embanked stretch was already showing tendencies to get stable—responding to the erosion-accretion cycle mentioned earlier. The entire length of this embankment is now completely covered by sand due to beach aggradation and foredune formation.

It is well known and was seen along the Medinipur coast in 1864 that dunes

Fig.6 Location of the erosion-preventing and disaster management schemes of Sagar island. (Modified after Bandyopadhyay, 1997a)

Fig.7 : (A) Protection from seasonal erosion of river-facing earthen embankments (background) can be prevented by brick paving (foreground). Two Examples from (i) Kachuberiya and (ii) Sumatinagar. (B) Alternatively, mangrove buffers (background) also offer protection from erosion (foreground). Example from Bankimnagar. (C) An ideal example from Radhakrishnapur-Bahirplot, showing erosion prevention by mangrove plantations as well as paved embankment.

work as effective natural embankments against storm surges (Gastrell 1868). In a retreating coast, landward migration of dunes that keep pace with coastal retrogradation should therefore never be prevented. Conversely, in Shibpur-Botkhali (the area having the highest erosion rate in Sagar for many years), a *Casuarina equisetifolia* farm forest was developed with intention of stabilising a foredune belt in 1987. The stabilisation, predictably, lead to almost complete destruction of the dune belt (Fig. 4).

As seen before, the coastal erosion of Sagar took place irrespective of the mangrove-covered and reclaimed areas of the island. Therefore, while new mangrove plantations may somewhat reduce the pace of erosion, they will not be able to stop it altogether. Moreover, away from the sheltered pockets like creek mouths, providing ideal conditions for their growth, the plantations failed noticeably where they are most needed in the presently eroding stretches of the coastline (Table 4).

Hence, there is a need for appreciation of the natural changes and cycles operating in a coastal area before any modification is attempted in it. It is not uncommon that an apparent short-term adversity (to the humans!) may form a part of natural feedback mechanism that turns out to be beneficial in the long run and on a wider perspective (Pethick 1992). Further, as noted by Goudie (1990:246), 'frequently coastal erosion has been accelerated as a result of human efforts to reduce it'. It is possible that the steep sea-ward gradient of Sagar's unpaved coastal embankments (Table 3), causing wave reflection, is actually aiding the process of erosion rather than preventing it.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The major feedback characteristics of the physical and human systems that are in some way related to the coastal erosion of Sagar island and its possible mitigation are shown in Fig. 8. This model and the following recommendations should also be applicable to most other areas of the reclaimed Sundarban, where the human-environment system operates on a similar level.

While ideally it is necessary to open wide areas of the island margin (extent depending on local conditions) to the tidal prism and wetland restoration for easing the pace of erosion, this is hard to translate into immediate reality. Considering the population pressure of the island itself (681 persons/km² in 1991 — projected to reach 1000 persons/km² by 2001) as well as the surrounding region, it would not be easy to address the immense problem of relocation this would cause.

It seems that a practical short-term approach (c. 5-15 yr) to the problem would be to form a central NEH-managing body and, since a large outlay is hard to come by for an underdeveloped area, to mobilise the existing resources more rationally. Broadly, the coast of Sagar can be divided into two major coastal zones: the river-facing eastern and western areas and the sea-facing southern stretch. In the former, strict time-bound periodic maintenance of the earthen embankments and paving them with bricks where they are not (or, through replantation, cannot be) protected by mangrove buffers, should bring tangible results. For the latter, which is comparatively more exposed to wave attack, alterations in the designs of the existing management

Fig. 8 : Relationship between the different components of the physical and human systems on the perspective of erosion hazard, Sagar island. Continuous lines (—) indicate links inducing positive feedback and dashed lines (---) denote links inducing negative feedback.

structures (e.g. a gentler embankment slope for less impeded wave run up) should be considered. Interaction with other nations, facing similar problems in similar or slightly different socio-economic conditions, may be of considerable help in this respect. It is often seen that the persons damaging the coastal plantation mostly belong to the interior areas of the island who are not immediately threatened by erosion of the marginal areas. Therefore, environment education and controlling of anthropogenic pressure need to be given top priorities in the island. Considering its adverse effect on morphological steady state of estuary, fresh reclamation for resettlement projects should never be attempted along the coasts. When attempted in the newly reclaimed intertidal mudflats along the interior creeks, their benefits should be carefully weighted against possible future adversities – as this would lead to invariable deterioration of the creeks concerned.

In the long term, in view of the projected greenhouse-induced increases in relative sea level (Saha 1991; Broadus 1993) and magnitude/frequency of tropical storms that may further accelerate the erosion of Sagar, a plan for eventual abandonment of the island should be prepared. However, since a community's vulnerability to an NEH-Impact is to a very great extent depends on its socio-economic conditions (O'Keefe *et al.* 1976), unreluctant developments efforts for the inhabitants of the Sundarban region would perhaps lead to the most permanent long-term solution to the erosion hazard in future.

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